
THE IMPORTANCE OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION AND FAMILY COOPERATION IN EDUCATING A CHILD AS A PERFECT HUMAN BEING

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8133484>

Daughter of Avezova Makhliyo Sultannazir

student of preschool education at Urganch State University, Faculty of Pedagogy

Abstract

If the family is the first place of education , the preschool is the second place of education. This article talks about the importance of preschool education and the cooperation of the child's family in the formation of a child as a perfect person. Also, the opinions and opinions of thinkers about the importance of family education in child's education are presented. The successful aspects of the mutual cooperation of the educator and the parents are also included in this article.

Key words

activity, team, sociometric, social, socialization, perfect person, image, status, need.

INTRODUCTION. The primary focus of social education is the family, and it is the father and mother who instill the initial social skills into the child's mind and sharpen his will. Family relations help the child not only to realize his identity as a person, but also to perceive himself as a representative of one or another gender and to improve his personal qualities. Observations have proven that the completeness of the family , i.e., where both the father and the mother live in peace and there are normal human relationships, a healthy spiritual environment, the all-round good development of the child, healthy, allows him to grow into a smart, strong-willed person. The need for a child to have both a father and a mother is explained by the fact that, for example, if a girl imagines what kind of mother she will be in the future, depending on her mother and her behavior in the family, in addition to realizing that she belongs to the female gender, Depending on their attitude, boys also define their future role in some way. So, the family is a pedagogical environment that is of great importance in the child's readiness for social relations. Therefore, scientists always recognize that one of the most important and primary tasks of the family is the educational function.

Here, it is worth noting that in the process of socialization of the child, the role and importance of pre-school education centers and schools are also important. But

everyone knows that the effectiveness of their education depends primarily on family upbringing, the meaning of the proverb "What one sees in a bird's nest, one does." The advantage of family socialization in front of special educational institutions is that all interactions in the family are carried out in a natural environment, based on the principle of human relations .[1]

MAIN PART. The growing generation's full acceptance of society's norms, becoming a good and necessary person of their time, is directly dependent on the relationships that the family establishes with other places of education. The role of preschool educational institutions in the process of socialization is of particular importance. Because the employees of preschool educational institutions communicate directly with the child's parents on a daily basis, and they perform two different functions than the school administration: formal and informal. In addition, the educator himself is in two different positions in relation to parents - as an official educator and as a sincere, attentive interlocutor. But it is not so easy to coordinate the work of family members and the employees of preschool educational institutions in raising one child, to achieve good results. Because only if both parties trust each other can there be sincere communication between them and positive results can be achieved in education.

We can distinguish a number of pedagogical features of such successful relationships:

- First of all, the educator shows the child only in a good way to the parents

should know . That is, only if the image of the child in the kindergarten is positive for the parents, they will bring their child from home with a good mood, and even when going home, they can say a warm goodbye to the teacher and teach the child that he should respect him and listen to what he says in the lessons. Otherwise, the parent will bring the child to kindergarten in pain and may teach him to ignore the rules of the preschool. So, the educator should be able to create a positive image of the child in the preschool educational institution in the parents.

- Preschool educators with parents

they should be able to show the child's achievements, knowledge, skills and abilities in daily communication. For example, how he behaved in communication with his peers, whether he has friends, how he was able to master a given poem or other task today, how he was able to help, and how he was able to informally inform about his sociometric status need So, informing the parents about the child's achievements strengthens the cooperation between the parents and the educator and helps the child to become a perfect person.

- The teacher knows the child's behavior and achievements or shortcomings at home

stand . This is determined through a trust-based dialogue process with the parent. Because if the educator does not know how the child behaves at home, his habits and actions, he will not be able to organize a proper pedagogical approach to him. Knowing the status of the child in the family, at home, is one of the best qualities of a teacher.

Taking the above into account in the child's socialization allows preschool educational institutions to work with the family under a single motto and achieve success. It should not be forgotten that the main interested party and the first person who shows activity should be the parents.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS . Ancient Greek philosophers Plato and Aristotle put forward the idea that the society should take over the upbringing of children, and the state should do all the necessary work in the education process. This idea was further developed in the works of the fantastic socialists of France, Saint Simon and Charles Faure. They put forward the idea that the state should mainly deal with child education. but eastern thinkers came to the conclusion that parents should deal with child education. With this, they paid great attention to the role of family education.

Rezauddin ibn Fakhriddin's treatise "Family" states that child education should not be done with malice and cowardice, but with patience, perseverance, kindness, endurance, compassion and sensitivity. It is a big mistake to keep a young baby unsupervised who cannot weigh the benefits and harms . Perhaps there are opinions that he should be brought up with justice between hardness and softness . [2]

It is known that from the age of 2-3, the child begins to express his needs, thoughts and demands somewhat clearly. He begins to question and scrutinize things that he can see and understand . Parents teach children how to look at our national qualities with love, and how to hate pride. Among our people, they talk about the achievements of great people. In teaching children to be humble and wise, it is useful to use as a basis the life examples of our scholars, such as the great Uzbek thinker Abu Ali ibn Sina, and the masterpiece ideas that they have left us as a legacy. Ibn Sina devoted a large chapter of his work "Tadbirul Manozil" to the issues of family education. In this work, he examines almost all aspects of people's family relationships . He makes great demands on the head of the family, emphasizes the need to know family education both theoretically and practically.

In his works, the thinker and scientist Abu Rayhan Beruni also thinks about the influence of the reputation of parents and educators on the child. This also meets current requirements. He says that all the power of parents' educational influence on children is based on reputation. However, this reputation is not given by nature, it is not created artificially, it is not achieved by fear, intimidation, or force, but it comes as a result of love for parents.

Alisher Navoi emphasizes that it is impossible to make mistakes in education. In fact, there are such mistakes in raising a child that they are reflected not only in the life of the family, but also in the life of society.

METHODOLOGY. It is possible to achieve positive results in the education of children thanks to skillfully combining the forms of work of the preschool educational institution with parents in a team style and individually, and organizing pedagogical campaigns among the general population. Here are some of the most common forms of cooperation of preschool education staff with parents and families:

- Work one-on-one with parents. Advanced pedagogical experiences shows that this type of work is very important. In this case, the educator studies the personal characteristics of the family and the child and takes them into account in his educational work. In the experience of our preschool educational institutions, various forms of one-on-one work with parents have been identified; visit of a tutor to the family, conducting a conversation for parents, giving them advice, familiarizing parents with the life of a preschool educational institution.
- Activities organized with parents as a team. These are parents Group and general meetings of mothers, parenting school, conferences, Saturdays, question-and-answer nights.
- Guided work . This type of work is demonstrative, children's work demonstrations , open-door days, pedagogical information stands, a library for parents, a folder with materials on all issues of family education.

Organization of joint activities of parents and employees of the preschool educational institution and its content depends on the conditions in the preschool educational institution. Mutual support, mutual understanding, and responsibility for assigned work are created where joint activities are carried out at the required level. Parents should help in greening the area of the preschool educational institution, preparing the rooms for the winter season, and carrying out sanitation works. The work of parents has a social character and should be based on discretion . [3]

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS. In short , working with families in preschool educational institutions has its own characteristics, which allows to raise a child as a perfect person. The preschool educational institution's system of working with the family should have clear goals and content. Analyzing the results of previous achievements and experiences in cooperation with parents , it is appropriate to carry out planned activities using various and interrelated forms and methods. The stronger the cooperation and the more it is built on human values , the better the effectiveness of education. The dreams of our people about the perfect person will be fulfilled and realized as a result of this cooperation. For this, it is necessary to increase the knowledge and understanding of parents about educational institutions, and to ensure that they understand that their children's perfection cannot be achieved without an educational institution.

REFERENCES :

1. Vasila Karimova. Family Psychology. - Tashkent: "Science and Technology", 2008.
2. Rezauddin ibn Fakhriddin. Family. - Tashkent: "Labor", 1991.
3. Nargiza Kayumova. Preschool pedagogy. - Tashkent: 2013.
4. BRDjurayeva, HMTojiboyeva, GMNazirova. Modern trends in education of children of preschool age. - Tashkent: UzPFITI, 2015.